

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D5.1

Analysis of alignment required to link and integrate with
Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
CCM	Copernicus Contributing Missions
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem
EO	Earth Observation
UDP	User Defined Process
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the initial findings from Task 5.1, which explored the integration of the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) openEO Federation with the TERRAVISION platform. The original objective was to leverage openEO's standardized API and the CDSE infrastructure to develop and expose scalable, reusable EO services. However, some practical limitations have been identified, especially concerning the accessibility of high-resolution, non-public Copernicus Contributing Mission (CCM) data, currently posing significant challenges to achieving the full objectives.

Although openEO provides a powerful abstraction layer for EO data processing, the reliance on private datasets substantially reduces the relevance and reusability of the resulting services in a larger community. As a result, while public Sentinel data remains accessible and usable via openEO, the integration of CCM data into service workflows might remain cumbersome and unscalable for the wider community.

Nonetheless, the CDSE openEO Federation remains a valuable asset for TERRAVISION. It supports several key activities: facilitating access to public EO data, enabling the development of Analysis Ready Data (ARD) workflows, publishing of reusable building blocks as services, and offering potential for deploying a dedicated TERRAVISION openEO backend. Collaboration between partners such as ICCS and VITO continues, with a shared interest in maximizing the integration of project results into the CDSE openEO Federation.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of T5.1 are to (i) carry out an analysis and the alignment required to create the link with the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, specifically focusing on integrating with OpenEO and (ii) facilitate the integration of the different services into the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem aiming to streamline the integration process and ensure that the services are fully functional and compatible with the existing infrastructure. Key activities include:

- Identification of key areas for improvement in OpenEO that will fully support data integration and service development within TERRAVISION.
- Create an architecture that supports the integration of EO-based, drone, and in-situ data in OpenEO (in collaboration with other tasks from WPs 4 & 5)
- Organizing sessions to ensure that everyone is aware of the general concepts of OpenEO and (co-)host a set of dedicated sessions to align the requirements for both the system and services with the cloud-agnostic approaches provided by OpenEO to ensure that the project is scalable and flexible enough to adapt to changing requirements and future developments.
- Assisting with other work packages in integrating their services into OpenEO.
- Enhancing the current OpenEO capabilities based on the improvements identified in Task 5.1.
- Onboarding of the various services into the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem marketplace.

H3 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The analysis and exploratory activities carried out under this deliverable led to several key outcomes:

- **Clarified integration limitations:** It was determined that while openEO can technically support private data processing, the added complexity and reduced accessibility hinder its value to the wider community when non-public datasets are involved.
- **Alternative strategies explored:** To address data access constraints, options such as hosting CCM data via TERRAVISION and CDSE STAC integration were explored.
- **Additional opportunities identified:** The potential of openEO to partly support Sentinel-based services, contribute to ARD generation, and serve as the basis for a dedicated TERRAVISION backend was recognized as promising.

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable focuses on the initial analysis and alignment between the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) and the TERRAVISION platform to support the initial development of services within the platform's scope. This document specifically addresses the service integration within the CDSE openEO Federation.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

The objectives related to this deliverable have not been fully realized due to the observations detailed in this document. In summary, although openEO supports the processing of any data, whether open or closed, the relevance of services to a larger community significantly diminishes whenever private data is required to execute the service. This limitation affects the accessibility and reusability of a service, as it necessitates additional steps to be performed by the user to access non-public data and make it available for openEO for processing.

While the integration of the final services into CDSE has become less relevant, the project has explored additional ways in which the CDSE openEO federation can support the development of the TERRAVISION platform.

1.3 Intended Audience

This deliverable presents an analysis of the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem openEO federation, detailing its application in supporting the TERRAVISION platform. The document contains information relevant to the following audiences:

- **Researchers and Scientists:** Focused on EO data analysis and integration, particularly within the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem openEO Federation.
- **Service Providers:** Developing EO-based services and applications.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable is structured to provide a comprehensive analysis of the integration between the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem openEO Federation and the TERRAVISION platform. The document is organized into several key sections, each addressing specific aspects of the integration process and its implications. The structure is as follows:

- **Platform Description:** This section provides an overview of the CDSE openEO Federation and its capabilities.
- **Integration Analysis:** This section presents a thorough analysis of the integration process, detailing the technical and practical challenges encountered.
- **Outcomes/Conclusions:** This section summarizes the key outcomes of the analysis, highlighting the main findings and their implications for the TERRAVISION platform.

The relationship between this deliverable and the relevant work packages is described below:

- **WP4:** This deliverable is related to WP4, which focuses on the architectural design of the TERRAVISION platform. The findings from this deliverable will inform the ongoing development and refinement of the platform's architecture.
- **WP5:** The integration process involves collaboration with WP5, responsible for other platforms providing data sources to the TERRAVISION services. The analysis and findings presented in this document result from activities carried out under WP5.
- **WP7:** The deliverable also has implications for WP7, focusing on developing the Analysis Ready Data (ARD) framework. Integrating the CDSE openEO Federation is considered to support ARD workflows development.
- **WP9:** This deliverable relates to WP9, responsible for developing the actual mining services. The content of this document is based on analyzing the requirements defined by the various tasks within WP9.

Through close cooperation with these work packages, this deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive and actionable analysis of the integration process.

2. CDSE openEO Federation

2.1 openEO: a unified API for Earth Observation Data Processing

openEO [1] is an open-source community standard aimed at standardizing and simplifying the access and processing of Earth Observation (EO) data across a variety of cloud platforms. It provides a common Application Programming Interface (API) along with a suite of tools and libraries that enable users to interact consistently with different EO cloud platforms, known as openEO backends, regardless of the underlying infrastructure.

Figure 1. Traditional integration of clients.

Figure 2. openEO API - Execute the same code on different backends.

Each openEO backend is responsible for managing the complexities associated with EO data processing, such as data retrieval, transformation, and parallel processing. This abstraction promotes interoperability, reproducibility, and scalability in EO data analysis, allowing users to concentrate on developing algorithms without being hindered by the technical challenges of large-scale data processing.

Key features of openEO include:

- **Multi-language Support:** Client libraries are available in Python, R, and JavaScript, allowing users to integrate openEO into their preferred programming environments.
- **Data Cube Concept:** openEO introduces the concept of "datacubes," multi-dimensional arrays that represent EO data in a structured format, simplifying complex analyses.
- **Process Graphs:** Users can construct workflows as process graphs, which can be executed across different backends, promoting Open Science principles.
- **Web Editor:** A graphical interface that allows users to build and execute workflows without extensive programming knowledge.

Figure 3. openEO Web Editor.

By providing these tools, openEO lowers the barrier to entry for EO data processing and encourages collaboration across the scientific community.

2.2 Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE): A Comprehensive EO Data Platform

The Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) [2] is a European initiative that offers immediate access to a vast repository of EO data, including both historical and current datasets from Sentinel satellites and other contributing missions. CDSE provides a suite of services and APIs that enable users to search, access, and process EO data efficiently.

Highlights of CDSE include:

- **Extensive Data Catalogue:** Users can explore a wide range of EO datasets through standardized APIs such as OData, STAC, and OpenSearch.

- **Cloud Computing Resources:** CDSE integrates cloud services from providers like CloudFerro and Open Telekom Cloud, allowing users to process data without the need for local infrastructure.
- **Ecosystem Collaboration:** The platform encourages the onboarding of third-party services, fostering a collaborative environment for developing new applications and services.

CDSE's infrastructure supports scalable and efficient EO data processing, making it a valuable resource for researchers, developers, and policymakers.

2.3 CDSE openEO Federation: Seamless Integration Across Platforms

The CDSE openEO federation [3] builds upon the concept of openEO, utilizing the CDSE cloud computing resources and represents a significant advancement in unifying access to and processing of EO data. By federating multiple openEO backends under a single interface, users can access and process datasets from various sources, such as CDSE and Terrascope, using the same authentication and API endpoints.

Figure 4. CDSE openEO Federation Architecture.

Benefits of the CDSE openEO federation include:

- **Unified Access Point:** Users can interact with multiple data and cloud providers through a single endpoint: <https://openeofed.dataspace.copernicus.eu>. The CDSE openEO federation automatically directs requests to the appropriate platform without any user intervention.
- **Simplified Authentication:** A common authentication mechanism eliminates the need for multiple accounts across different platforms.

- **Expanded Data and Cloud Computing Availability:** The federation provides access to a broader range of datasets and cloud computing resources, enhancing the potential for comprehensive analyses.

This federated approach streamlines the workflow for EO data users, promoting efficiency and interoperability across different platforms.

3. Integration with TERRAVISION Platform

3.1 Initial Scope

The initial objective of Task 5.1 was to investigate and analyze how the CDSE openEO federation could be harnessed to support the development of a suite of services within the TERRAVISION platform. These services would be designed for the combined usage of publicly hosted satellite datasets available on the CDSE infrastructure and data provided through the TERRAVISION environment, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. TERRAVISION Architecture as described in D4.4.

The overarching goal of this integration is to create processing services that not only support the specific needs of project demonstrators but are also generalizable and scalable, allowing them to be reused by a broader community of Earth Observation (EO) users. This strategy aligns seamlessly with the openEO philosophy, which promotes openness, interoperability, and modular development of EO processing services.

In particular, openEO facilitates the creation and deployment of User-Defined Processes (UDPs) [4], which are customized workflows encapsulated into a single callable process. These UDPs enable developers to abstract complex EO workflows into reusable, standardized

components that can be invoked by others without requiring detailed knowledge of the underlying implementation.

The concept of UDPs has a strong track record across numerous EO projects. Many ESA-funded initiatives, along with an increasing number of European projects, are already leveraging this approach to publish their algorithms as services on openEO-compliant platforms. These efforts primarily target large-scale satellite data processing. Additionally, emerging ESA initiatives such as EarthCODE and APEx position openEO as a key enabling technology, both to advance scientific research and to support seamless execution of services across multiple cloud platforms.

Within the CDSE context, such UDPs can be published and made accessible via the CDSE Algorithm Plaza [5], making them discoverable and executable by the wider CDSE user community. This mechanism ensures that innovative processing chains developed in TERRAVISION can be effectively shared, reused, and built upon—thereby increasing impact, fostering collaboration, and accelerating the uptake of EO technologies.

By aligning the TERRAVISION service development efforts with the openEO federation model and leveraging the publishing capabilities of the Algorithm Plaza, Task 5.1 aims to contribute directly to the long-term sustainability and community integration of the project’s outcomes.

3.2 Feedback from Service Providers

Throughout the first part of the project, the feasibility of the initial approach was further analyzed. Multiple sessions were conducted to introduce the concepts of openEO, followed by detailed discussions to identify which services would fit this concept. This resulted in the identification of the following services:

- Raw Material Exploration Service (T9.1; ICCS)
- EO-based monitoring of stockpile volumes and extraction rates (T9.3; ICCS)
- Primary and Secondary Raw Material Maps (T9.4; VITO)

As a result of these discussions and the completion of the first preliminary analysis by the service providers regarding their input data requirements, both ICCS and VITO indicated, although this analysis is not yet finalized, that the current data offerings provided through the CDSE openEO federation may lack sufficient resolution to support their service use cases. Consequently, they would need to rely on high-resolution data available through the Copernicus Contributing Missions (CCM).

Although the CCM data is hosted on CDSE, it is not classified as a public dataset. To access this data, a request must be submitted to CDSE, which must then be approved before the user can download it to their local environment. Unfortunately, this approach is incompatible with openEO. While openEO can load external data, it requires that the data is made available through a STAC-based catalogue to facilitate efficient selection and retrieval. Therefore, users would need to download the CCM data to their local machines and set up their own STAC-based catalogue to process the data through openEO. This approach is not scalable towards a larger user base.

This current method of accessing CCM data makes it less aligned with the initial goals of T5.1. Encapsulating services that require access to non-public data, such as CCM data, would not provide significant benefits to the community, as each user would need to request access to the data and ensure it can be processed by openEO.

It is important to note that CDSE is discussing plans to integrate the CCM data into their STAC catalogue. This integration would eliminate the need for users to ensure that data is available for openEO processing, as openEO would be able to interact directly with the CDSE STAC catalogue in that case. Nevertheless, usability for the larger community would still be limited, as each user would have to request dedicated access to the CCM data, which remains private. Currently, there is no specific roadmap outlining when this integration will occur, and it falls outside VITO's activities within CDSE.

Alternatively, TERRAVISION is also exploring the possibility of hosting the CCM data on the TERRAVISION platform and making it available through STAC. While this would alleviate the need for users to set up their STAC environment, it still requires them to request the data from CDSE and ensure it is available via the TERRAVISION platform, again impacting the overall user experience of using the final services.

In summary, if a service demands data access through an offline process, the relevance of exposing the service as a public UDP diminishes. However, it remains valuable to explore how the final service implementation can be integrated into openEO and the CDSE openEO federation as a whole. If integration via openEO proves unfeasible, deploying the service on the TERRAVISION Platform could be considered as an alternative solution.

3.3 Support for the TERRAVISION Platform

While the integration of the CDSE openEO federation to support service development and broader community upscaling presents certain challenges, both the CDSE openEO federation and CDSE as a whole remain valuable assets in supporting activities within the TERRAVISION platform. Several ideas and opportunities have been explored to leverage this support, as outlined in the following subsections.

3.3.1 Access to public Sentinel data

Several services under development, including the Primary and Secondary Raw Material Maps, continue to partly rely on Sentinel data to assess the capabilities and refine their workflows. For these services, openEO, along with additional CDSE tools, can facilitate data access by offering multiple mechanisms for downloading Sentinel datasets. This allows partners to retrieve relevant EO data for processing in their own local environments or the TERRAVISION platform, ensuring flexibility and autonomy during development.

3.3.2 Support for ARD Framework

In the context of WP8, the TERRAVISION project is designing a framework for the generation of Analysis Ready Data (ARD). While existing solutions have been reviewed, early discussions revealed that openEO also includes built-in capabilities that can support on-the-fly ARD

generation. In collaboration with WP8, these capabilities will be further explored and assessed against the specific requirements of TERRAVISION. Initial concepts, such as increased flexibility in Sentinel-1 data processing, are currently being evaluated and may be introduced as native features within the CDSE openEO federation.

3.3.3 Support for deployment of TERRAVISION openEO backend

Building on the architectural design from WP4, ICCS is actively exploring the deployment of a dedicated openEO backend to serve the data and services of the TERRAVISION platform. This effort is being carried out in close cooperation with VITO, using the open-source repositories maintained by the openEO community. Based on current progress, VITO has identified several areas for improvement to better support this deployment:

- Enhancement of technical documentation and tooling for setting up a custom openEO backend
- Improved support for loading external STAC collections, which would not only strengthen TERRAVISION's capabilities but also facilitate potential future integration with CCM and CDSE datasets

3.3.4 Continued support for service providers

Task 5.1 will remain actively involved in discussions on service integration within the openEO ecosystem, providing technical guidance and exploring viable pathways for incorporating TERRAVISION services into CDSE. In scenarios where a complete end-to-end service implementation proves infeasible, a modular publishing approach could be adopted. This would involve exposing individual service components or building blocks that are particularly relevant to the mining and raw materials community. Examples of such components include:

- ARD generation methods tailored to mining-related use cases
- Pre-processing algorithms for satellite imagery that can be downloaded and subsequently used within TERRAVISION workflows
- Post-processing steps, such as time series analytics, applied to outputs from the TERRAVISION platform
- Additional reusable processing elements of interest to the broader EO community

This continued collaboration ensures that valuable insights and technical innovations from TERRAVISION can be shared through the CDSE openEO federation, increasing their impact and fostering wider adoption across domains.

4. Conclusion

While the full integration of CDSE openEO Federation services into TERRAVISION has currently been constrained by data accessibility issues, particularly around non-public CCM data, the exploration has yielded valuable insights. There is still potential for openEO to foster open, interoperable, and reusable EO services, especially when used with publicly accessible datasets like Sentinel. Additionally, the project has successfully identified alternative strategies to enhance the development of Analysis Ready Data (ARD) workflows and support the deployment of the TERRAVISION openEO backend.

The project has shifted from full-service deployment within CDSE to identifying targeted ways in which CDSE and openEO capabilities can still enhance the project activities.

5. References

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